

Providing quality-assessed and standardised soil data to support global mapping and modelling (WoSIS snapshot 2023)

Niels H. Batjes, Luis Calisto, and Luis M. de Sousa

ISRIC – World Soil Information, Droevendaalsesteeg 3, 6708 PB Wageningen, the Netherlands

Correspondence: Niels H. Batjes (niels.batjes@isric.org)

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Abstract. Snapshots derived from the World Soil Information Service (WoSIS) are served freely to the international community. These static datasets provide quality-assessed and standardised soil profile data that can be used to support digital soil mapping and environmental applications at broad scale levels. Since the release of the preceding snapshot in 2019, refactored ETL (extract, transform and load) procedures for screening, ingesting and standardising disparate source data have been developed. In conjunction with this, the WoSIS data model was overhauled, making it compatible with the ISO 28258 and Observations and Measurements (O&M) domain models. Additional procedures for querying, serving and downloading the publicly available standardised data have been implemented using open software (e.g. GraphQL API). Following up on a short discussion of these methodological developments we discuss the structure and content of the “WoSIS 2023 snapshot”. A range of new soil datasets was shared with us, registered in the ISRIC World Data Centre for Soils (WDC-Soils) data repository and subsequently processed in accordance with the licences specified by the data providers. An important effort has been the processing of forest soil data collated in the framework of the EU-HoliSoils project. We paid special attention to the standardisation of soil property definitions, description of the soil analytical procedures and standardisation of the units of measurement. The 2023 snapshot considers soil chemical properties (total carbon, organic carbon, inorganic carbon (total carbonate equivalent), total nitrogen, phosphorus (extractable P, total P and P retention), soil pH, cation exchange capacity and electrical conductivity) and physical properties (soil texture (sand, silt and clay), bulk density, coarse fragments and water retention), grouped according to analytical procedures that are operationally comparable. Method options are defined for each analytical procedure (e.g. pH measured in water, KCl or CaCl₂ solution, molarity of the solution, and soil / solution ratio). For each profile we also provide the original soil classification (i.e. FAO, WRB and USDA system with their version) and pedological horizon designations as far as these have been specified in the source databases. Three measures for “fitness for intended use” are provided to facilitate informed data use: (a) positional uncertainty of the profile’s site location, (b) possible uncertainty associated with the operationally defined analytical procedures and (c) date of sampling. The most recent (i.e. *dynamic*) dataset, called *wosis_latest*, is freely accessible via various web services. To permit consistent referencing and citation, we also provide a *static* snapshot (in this case, December 2023). This snapshot comprises quality-assessed and standardised data for 228 000 geo-referenced profiles. The data come from 174 countries and represent more than 900 000 soil layers (or horizons) and over 6 million records. The number of measurements for each soil property varies (greatly) between profiles and with depth, this generally depending on the objectives of the initial soil sampling programmes. In the coming years, we aim to gradually fill gaps in the geographic distribution of the profiles, as well as in the soil observations themselves, this subject to the sharing of a wider selection of “public” soil data by prospective data contributors; possible solutions for this are discussed. The WoSIS 2023 snapshot is archived and freely available at <https://doi.org/10.17027/isric-wdcsoils-20231130> (Calisto et al., 2023).

1 Introduction

The World Soil Information Service (WoSIS) draws on a large complement of soil profile data that have been shared by numerous data providers. Nonetheless, a large proportion of the 800 000 “so-called” freely available soil profiles (see Arrouays et al., 2017), in practice, still remain “inaccessible” due to various licence constraints (e.g. Cornu et al., 2023). Soil data submitted for consideration in WoSIS come from a wide range of legacy holdings (e.g. traditional soil surveys) and increasingly include data derived from proximal sensing (e.g. Shepherd et al., 2022; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2016). The source data come in various formats and were determined according to a range of field sampling and soil analytical procedures, requiring standardisation and harmonisation during their ingestion/processing into WoSIS.

Prior to discussing the “2023 snapshot”, we provide a short retrospective of activities that led to the development of WoSIS. In the early days of desktop computers, ISRIC with its partners compiled a range of project-specific databases such as ISIS (van de Ven and Tempel, 1994), created to manage data for the ISRIC World Soil Reference Collection; several national- and continental-scale SOil and TERrain (SOTER) databases (e.g. FAO and ISRIC, 2003; FAO et al., 2007, 1998); the WISE database (Batjes, 1997; Batjes and Bridges, 1994); and the Africa Soil Profiles Database (AfSP) (Leenaars et al., 2014). While these different databases were structured along the general principles and criteria of the FAO Guidelines for Soil Description (FAO, 1977, 2006) and USDA Soil Survey Manual (Soil Survey Division Staff, 1993), the ISIS, SOTER, WISE and AfSP databases each had their own data models and conventions. Further, out of necessity at the time, the databases were developed and implemented on stand-alone computers using a range of commercial software packages. In 2009, ISRIC management decided to bring the above stand-alone products together in a centralised enterprise database, known as WoSIS (World Soil Information Service), developed using PostgreSQL with the PostGIS extension for handling spatial data. After the initial ingestion and standardisation of the above “ISRIC holdings”, the service was to be expanded with datasets shared by a diverse range of soil data providers.

The original aim of WoSIS was to accommodate any type of soil data (profile, vector and grid) (Ribeiro et al., 2015; Tempel et al., 2013). However, from 2015 onwards, in view of technical considerations and institutional developments, the scope of WoSIS was changed to “safeguarding, processing, standardising and serving geo-referenced soil profile (point) data for the world” (Ribeiro et al., 2020). Alternatively, vector and grid maps derived from traditional soil mapping (e.g. Batjes, 2016; Dijkshoorn et al., 2005; FAO et al., 2012; van Engelen et al., 2006) and digital soil mapping (e.g. Hengl et al., 2017; Poggio et al., 2021; Turek et al.,

2023) would be managed and served through other components of our spatial data infrastructure, such as the ISRIC Data Hub (<https://data.isric.org>, last access: 24 April 2024) and the SoilGrids/WoSIS portal (<https://soilgrids.org>, last access: 24 April 2024). All these web services were developed using free and open-source software (FOSS).

The ultimate goal of WoSIS, like for related global data compilation activities (Baritz et al., 2017; de Sousa et al., 2019), is full data harmonisation (Batjes et al., 2020; Ribeiro et al., 2015, 2020). According to the Global Soil Partnership (GSP; Baritz et al., 2014), harmonisation involves “providing mechanisms for the collation, analysis and exchange of consistent and comparable global soil data and information” and considers the following domains: (a) soil description, classification and mapping; (b) soil analyses; (c) exchange of digital soil data; and (d) interpretations. In view of the breadth and magnitude of the task, as well as the limited availability of comparative “multiple analytical procedures” datasets as required for full harmonisation (Batjes, 2023; Bispo et al., 2021; van Leeuwen et al., 2022), we have limited ourselves to the standardisation of soil property definitions, soil analytical procedure descriptions, plausibility checks for soil observation values and the standardisation of measurement units for commonly required soil properties (see Appendix A). Importantly, users should always keep in mind that the source datasets themselves (e.g. Armas et al., 2023; NPDB, 2023; USDA-NCSS, 2021) will provide more detailed information than WoSIS, albeit not in a consistent, globally standardised format.

This paper discusses methodological changes to the WoSIS workflow and new data additions since the release of the previous snapshot (Batjes et al., 2020). First, we describe the new data model and the refactored data screening/ingestion process and indicate how the “shared” data are being served to the user community upon their standardisation. Thereafter, we describe the actual data screening, quality control and standardisation process. Subsequently, we describe the spatial distribution of soil profile sites and list the number of soil observations represented in the “WoSIS 2023 snapshot” (hereafter referred to as the 2023 snapshot). In conjunction with this, we provide three measures for “fitness for intended use” of the standardised data and discuss possible limitations of the snapshot. Finally, following up on a discussion concerning the scope for “full data harmonisation” in WoSIS, future developments and possible constraints arising are outlined.

The naming conventions and standard units of measurement are listed in Appendix A, while the structure of the snapshot files is described in Appendix B. In Appendix C we list the number of sites by country/area and continent (Table C1) as well as their distribution by World Terrestrial Ecosystems (Table C2) and biomes (Table C3).

Soils are important providers of ecosystem services (FAO and ITPS, 2015). WoSIS-served data have been used for a range of applications, such as predictive soil property mapping (Guevara et al., 2018; Moulatlet et al., 2017; Nenkam et al., 2022; Poggio et al., 2021; Turek et al., 2023), space and time modelling of soil organic carbon stock change (Heuvelink et al., 2021), and a diverse range of environmental assessments (e.g. Hassani et al., 2024; Huang et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2021; Lutz et al., 2019; Maire et al., 2015; Sanderman et al., 2017; Sothe et al., 2022). For example, based on the “2016 snapshot” and “2019 snapshot” respectively, Ivushkin et al. (2019) mapped global soil salinity change, while Wang et al. (2024) analysed responses of soil organic carbon under warming across global biomes. Ultimately, such information can help to inform the global conventions such as the UNCCD (United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification) and UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) so that policy-makers and business leaders can make informed decisions about the environment, biodiversity and human well-being at an appropriate scale level.

2 WoSIS data model and workflow

2.1 Workflow

The data model and workflow for acquiring, ingesting, processing and serving data as described in Ribeiro et al. (2020) were overhauled. This proved necessary as this procedure was essentially designed as a series of dataset-specific Python and SQL scripts, which was adequate as long as WoSIS was still relatively small. However, in view of the rapidly growing population of shared soil data and overall complexity of the data model itself, it proved necessary to implement a new, state-of-the-art ISO domain model (de Sousa, 2023; de Sousa et al., 2023), with refactored ETL (extract, transform and load) procedures, to ultimately better serve our diverse user community in our capacity as the World Data Centre for Soils (WDC-Soils).

The main stages of the new workflow are visualised in Fig. 1: (a) data providers share their data with ISRIC WDC-Soils; (b) the submitted datasets with associated metadata are screened for “completeness of information provided” (e.g. the licence defining access rights and description of terms and units) and, once considered adequate, subsequently stored “as is” in the WDC-Soils data repository (see “ISRIC Admin” in Fig. 1); and (c) the source datasets are imported into the new WoSIS PostgreSQL relational database (see Sect. 2.2), using refactored ETL procedures (see Sect. 2.3). Step (c) includes (c1) basic data quality assessment and control, (c2) standardising descriptions for the soil analytical procedures and units of measurement, and (c3) automated checks against plausibility limits for each soil observation; see Sect. 3 for details. Subsequently, (d) the quality-assessed and standardised data are distributed via

various services such as dashboards and WFS (OpenGIS web feature service) as well as a metadata catalogue service.

2.2 Data model

As indicated earlier, a new data model for WoSIS was developed, aligned where possible with the ISO 28258 domain model (de Sousa et al., 2023) and the GloSIS web ontology (Palma et al., 2024), both stemming from O&M (Observations and Measurement; Cox and David, 2011), all the while preserving legacy data. Main features of interest are the dataset (describes source of data), site (geo-spatial location where a soil investigation took place) and profile (sequence of pedogenetic horizons along the depth of the profile). The key modification vis à vis the previous data model (Ribeiro et al., 2020) is the conditioning of analytical methods to the observation (see <https://git.wur.nl/isric/databases/wosis-docs>, last access: 26 April 2024). Changes made to the database schema and data over time are tracked using a migration tool (<https://github.com/graphile/migrate>, last access: 24 April 2024). It maintains a record of the history; state; and dependencies of the database, including the conversion to the new data model.

Special attention was paid to the succinct description of the analytical procedures (see c2 above) using seven database tables, as summarised below:

- `thes_method_value`. The thesaurus of values that match the keys is used to define an analytical method, for example, “natural clod” for the “sample type” key for the “bulk density” method.
- `thes_method_key`. This is the thesaurus of keys that is used to define an analytical method, for example, “reported pH”, “exchange solution” and “index cation”.
- `thes_method_option`. This encodes the possible combinations of key–value pairs for each numerical observation on layers. Note that only a small subset of observations can be associated with particular method options.
- `method_source`. Analytical method descriptions are as defined in the respective source databases (i.e. prior to standardisation). This table was imported as is from the old data model (Ribeiro et al., 2020) with the addition of a synthetic primary key. The records in this table remain essential to identify the method referred by each result.
- `method_standard`. This distinguishes each source method by the particular observation to which it applies. It can be regarded as a standardised description of the source method. Each record corresponds to a collection of key–value pairs in the `method_option` table for a single observation. Results for numerical observations

Figure 1. Schematic WoSIS workflow for ingesting, standardising and distributing soil profile data.

reference this table to identify the corresponding analytical method.

- `method_option_standard`. This defines a many-to-many relationship between the `method_standard` and `method_option` tables. It determines the exact collection of key–value option pairs that constitute a standard method. The standard method is a specialisation of the source method for a specific observation.

2.3 ETL procedure

Extract, transform and load (ETL) is a standardised, semi-automatic process that guides the data processor during the ingestion of new datasets. Refactored ETL procedures were developed to align with the structure of the ISO data model. During the initial phase, newly shared datasets are submitted to a quick consistency check (i.e. format, data model, metadata and licence) after which they are uploaded as is to a staging area in the WoSIS system. Subsequently, during the transform stage the uploaded datasets are parsed by the system. During this process, validation and standardisation occur (see Sect. 3.3 for details). In the case of (possible) unconformities the system will generate descriptive messages that guide the data processor towards possible actions that

may be needed to resolve the flagged unconformities. The data processor then needs to correct these issues in conformity with the requirements of the WoSIS procedure manual in steps guided by the system; in some cases the original data providers may need to be consulted. At the end of this phase, the cleaned and standardised data remain in the staging area for final verification by a soil expert. After this verification, the final stage of the ETL process, “load”, can start. This is a fully automated process during which the cleaned and standardised data are copied into the WoSIS database and subsequently removed from the staging area (note that the source data themselves are permanently preserved in the ISRIC data repository). The newly ingested data can now be used to create a range of WoSIS-derived products (e.g. *wosis_latest*, *wosis_internal* and dashboards; see Fig. 1) in accordance with the licences and possible restrictions specified by the data providers.

2.4 Operational definitions

Soil characteristics, such as texture, bulk density and organic carbon content, are collated according to a wide range of procedures in different countries. For such incongruent data to be interpreted correctly during the ETL process, the procedures for their collection, analysis and reporting need to be

well documented and understood. Results can differ when different analytical procedures are used, even though these procedures may carry the same name (e.g. clay, silt and sand size fraction) or concept (see Soil Survey Staff, 2011). This makes the inter-comparison of different datasets difficult if it is not known how these data were collected/analysed. Therefore we use “operational definitions”, as defined by USDA Soil Survey Staff (2011), for soil properties that are linked to specific analytical procedures. To properly characterise the “pH of a soil”, for example, we need information on sample pre-treatment, soil / solution ratio and description of solution (e.g. H₂O, 1 M KCl, 0.02 M CaCl₂ or 1 M NaF). Soil pH measured in sodium fluoride (pH NaF), for example, provides a measure for the phosphorus (P) retention of a soil, whereas pH measured in water (pH H₂O) is an indicator for soil nutrient status. Consequently, in WoSIS, soil properties are named according to and defined by the analytical procedures and corresponding “method options”, based on common practice in soil science (e.g. BDFIOD for “bulk density (BD), fine earth fraction (FI), oven dry (OD)”). The current list of soil properties standardised in WoSIS is described in Sect. 3.3.

2.5 Data provisioning

Upon completion of the semi-automated ETL process, the quality-assessed and standardised data are distributed freely through various channels (see Fig. 1), this in accordance with the license agreements (see Sect. 2.6):

- Through *wosis_latest* (*dynamic*), the data are served via WFS, the respective endpoints are catalogued at the ISRIC Data Hub (https://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search?any=wosis_latest, last access: 26 April 2024).
- The data are also served as “fixed” snapshots (in TSV format) with a unique digital object identifier (DOI) to permit consistent citation (https://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search?any=wosis_snapshot, last access: 26 April 2024).
- The contents of *wosis_latest* can also be visualised using a dashboard with some querying and zooming facilities (https://dashboards.isric.org/superset/dashboard/wosis_latest, last access: 26 April 2024).
- Profile data from *wosis_latest* can also be queried through the “SoilGrids web platform” (<https://soilgrids.org/>, last access: 26 April 2024), which also provides access to a range of soil property maps derived from the WoSIS-served profile data and a set of environmental covariates using digital soil mapping (Poggio et al., 2021; Turek et al., 2023).

- The *wosis_latest* holdings can also be queried using a GraphQL interface (<https://graphql.isric.org/>, last access: 26 April 2024) that facilitates exploration of the data (e.g. select data for organic carbon, bulk density and proportion of coarse fragments per layer (horizon) for profiles located in a given geography). Results of such tailor-made queries can then be exported as input in scripting languages such as Python or R (R Core Team, 2021), for example to calculate regional carbon stocks.

2.6 Licence agreements

It is not a simple task to find potential providers of “open” soil data (Arrouays et al., 2017; Batjes, 2009; Cornu et al., 2023). This may be due to technical issues, access arrangements, reasons for sharing (e.g. “Why share the data and for what purpose? What is in it for us?”), and legal requirements (Bispo et al., 2021; Robinson et al., 2019). All datasets that are shared with our centre are first registered in the ISRIC Data Repository together with their metadata; data sharing agreements should align with the ISRIC Data Policy (ISRIC, 2016). During the subsequent WoSIS standardisation workflow, we are faced with three different types of datasets: first, those with a non-restrictive Creative Commons (CC-BY) licence, defined here as at least a CC-BY (Attribution) or CC-BY-NC (Attribution Non-Commercial) licence (these are later served as *wosis_latest*); second, datasets with a more “restrictive” licence in the sense that they can exclusively be used for “visualisations”, such as SoilGrids™ (i.e. *wosis_internal*; see Fig. 1), by ISRIC itself (the latter generally because the coordinates cannot be disclosed as stipulated by certain data providers; for details see <https://www.isric.org/explore/wosis/wosis-contributing-institutions-and-experts>, last access: 26 April 2024); and finally, several datasets with licences that stipulate that they should only be safeguarded in the ISRIC repository and cannot be used for any data processing (i.e. permanent embargo).

The number of profiles in WoSIS per licence category, i.e. “public” and “restricted”, can be viewed and filtered using a dashboard (https://dashboards.isric.org/superset/dashboard/wosis_licenses/, last access: 26 April 2024). As shown in Table 1, the number of “public access” profiles served from WoSIS as snapshots increased from 96 000 in 2016 to 228 000 in 2023. Conversely, it should be noted here that a large proportion of the forest soil data shared in the framework of the EU-HoliSoils project, for instance, could not be included in the “2023 snapshot” due to licence restrictions specified by the data providers. As a result, only 34 000 out of the total of 107 000 profiles shared with ISRIC between 2019 and 2023 could actually be included in the 2023 snapshot (i.e. *wosis_latest*).

Table 1. Number of soil profiles and properties served in successive WoSIS snapshots.

Snapshot	No. of profiles	No. of properties*
Jul 2016	96 000	22
Sep 2019	196 000	45
Dec 2023	228 000	45

* Property names are based on “operational definitions”, i.e. a combination of a property and procedure in the terminology of the WoSIS data model (see Sects. 2.4 and 3.3).

3 Data screening, quality control and standardisation

3.1 Consistency checks

Soil profile data shared for possible consideration in WoSIS were sampled and analysed according to various national or international standards and presented in various formats (from paper to digital). They are of varying degrees of completeness as discussed below. To be considered in the WoSIS standardisation workflow (Fig. 1), each soil profile must meet several criteria, as described earlier in Batjes et al. (2020, p. 301). In summary, they must be associated with a site correctly geo-referenced, have consistently defined upper and lower depths for each layer (or pedogenetic horizon), and have observations for at least some of the soil properties that are being served (e.g. sand, silt, clay and pH) as well as a succinct description of the analytical procedures and units of measurement. A soil (taxonomic) classification is considered desirable though not mandatory. Profiles associated with a valid site, for which only the classification is specified in the source data, can still be useful for mapping of soil taxonomic classes.

Consistency in layer depth (i.e. sequential increase in the upper and lower depth reported for each layer down the profile) is checked using automated procedures (see Sect. 3.2). In line with current internationally accepted conventions, such depth increments are given as “measured from the soil surface, including organic layers and mineral covers” (FAO, 2006; IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022; Schoeneberger et al., 2012; Soil Survey Staff, 2022b). Until 1993, however, the beginning (zero datum) of the profile was set at the top of the mineral surface (the *solum* proper), except for “thick” organic layers, as defined for peat soils (FAO, 1977, 1990). Organic horizons were recorded as above and mineral horizons recorded as below, relative to the mineral surface (Schoeneberger et al., 2012, p. 2–6). As far as possible, such “organic_surface” layers are flagged in the snapshot (see Appendix B) so that they may be filtered out during auxiliary computations of soil organic carbon stocks, for example.

3.2 Screening for duplicate profiles

In the early stage of WoSIS, many source databases were compilations of shared soil profile data necessitating intricate procedures for identifying and flagging possibly repeated profiles (see Batjes et al., 2017; Ribeiro et al., 2020). Soil profiles located within 100 m of each other are flagged as possible duplicates, provided the year of sampling is identical (this criterion allows for reporting results of soil monitoring campaigns at the same site). Upon additional automated checks concerning the thickness of the first three soil layers (i.e. upper and lower depth), sand, silt and clay content, the duplicate profiles with the least-comprehensive component of observations are flagged and excluded from further processing (i.e. distribution). When still in doubt after these rigorous tests, a final visual “similarity check” is made with respect to other commonly reported soil properties such as pH_{water} and organic carbon content, possibly leading to the flagging (exclusion) of some additional profiles.

3.3 Standardisation of property names, analytical procedure descriptions and units of measurement

A crucial step during data ingestion is the standardisation of the, regularly non-English, soil property names used in the source databases to the WoSIS conventions, as well as the standardisation of the soil analytical procedures according to consistent “operational definitions” (see Appendix A). Subsequently, the units of measurement are standardised and the reported measurement values assessed according to soil-observation-specific plausibility ranges for the respective soil properties (i.e. likely minimum and maximum). Some of these plausibility limits may change when more data become available for soil observations that are so far under-represented, similar to ICP Forests (2020, p. 25), and appropriate PostgreSQL “trigger mechanisms” have been implemented for this. Data that do not meet these conditions are flagged and not processed further in the ETL workflow (see above), unless the observed “inconsistencies” can easily be solved (e.g. blatant typos in pH values). Alternatively, the data provider(s) may be contacted to resolve the observed errors.

Similar to the 2019 snapshot, the following soil properties are considered in the 2023 snapshot:

- *Chemical*. Properties include total carbon (i.e. organic plus inorganic carbon), organic carbon, inorganic carbon (i.e. total carbonate equivalent), total nitrogen, soil pH, cation exchange capacity, electrical conductivity and phosphorus (extractable P, total P and P retention).
- *Physical*. Properties include soil texture (clay, silt, sand), coarse fragments, bulk density and water retention.

All measurement values are served as recorded in the source data, after the above consistency checks and standardisa-

tion of the units of measurement to the target units (see Appendix A). As such, we *do not* apply any “gap-filling” procedures during ETL, nor do we apply any pedotransfer functions (PTFs) to derive missing bulk density data or soil hydrological properties or harmonise particle class size limits to a common standard, for example. This follow-up stage of data processing is seen as the task of the data users (modellers) themselves. In practice, the required PTFs or ways for depth-aggregating the layer data will be determined by the projected use(s) of the standardised data (see Finke, 2006; Heuvelink et al., 2021; Poggio et al., 2021; Turek et al., 2023; van Leeuwen et al., 2024; Van Looy et al., 2017). It should be noted, however, that inadvertently some PTF-derived values (e.g. for bulk density) could have slipped through the above consistency checks in situations where procedures were mis-coded in the metadata of a source dataset; critical modellers should exclude such values during their analyses.

3.4 Providing measures for fitness for intended use

As indicated earlier, data served from WoSIS are used for a wide range of environmental applications (e.g. Guevara et al., 2018; Heuvelink et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2021; Maire et al., 2015; Moulatlet et al., 2017; Poggio et al., 2021; Sanderman et al., 2017; Sothe et al., 2022; Turek et al., 2023), but many of these assessments do not explicitly consider the uncertainties that are associated with the data. However, it is well known that “soil observations used for calibration and interpolation are themselves not error-free” (e.g. Baroni et al., 2017; Cressie and Kornak, 2003; Folberth et al., 2016; Grimm and Behrens, 2010; Guevara et al., 2018; Heuvelink, 2014; van Leeuwen et al., 2022). Therefore, since 2019, we have provided three measures for fitness for intended use in *wosis_latest*, namely (a) positional uncertainty of the profiles (i.e. site location), (b) inferred accuracy of the laboratory measurements and (c) date of sampling. These three measures, although approximative, should be duly considered in digital soil mapping and subsequent earth system modelling as they can affect the prediction uncertainty and “area of applicability” of the resulting derived products (Dai et al., 2019; Meyer and Pebesma, 2021; Shi et al., 2023). For example, large areas of the globe are still poorly represented in WoSIS (basically the yellow areas in Fig. 3). As indicated earlier, this issue can only be remedied when a larger selection of datasets is shared by the international soil community for consideration in WoSIS.

Importantly, prospective data users should also realise that the point/profile data shared for consideration in WoSIS are largely based on purposive sampling. During such “traditional” surveys, soil surveyors identify sample locations based on their knowledge of the survey area, desired level of detail (scale) and objective of the survey, for example detailed or exploratory surveys (FAO, 2006; IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022; Soil Survey Staff, 2017). Hence, such “legacy” data are not based on a probabilistic sampling

Table 2. Positional uncertainty of profile site locations.

Positional uncertainty	Number of profiles	
	<i>n</i>	%
~ 100 m	195 554	86
100 m–1 km	21 653	9
1–10 km	3846	2
Over 10 km	7037	3

scheme, as recommended for digital soil mapping (Brus et al., 2011; Brus, 2022; Cramer et al., 2019; Heuvelink et al., 2007).

3.4.1 Positional uncertainty

Profiles in WoSIS are geo-referenced through the site in which they were sampled in accordance with ISO 28258 standards (de Sousa et al., 2023). The coordinates themselves are presented according to the World Geodetic System datum ensemble (i.e. WGS84, EPSG code 4326) upon their conversion from a diverse range of national projections. For most profiles (86 %; see Table 2) the approximate positional uncertainty of the profile locations, as inferred from the coordinates given in the source datasets, is ~ 100 m. Typically, geo-referencing before the advent of GPS (Global Positioning Systems) in the 1970s is less accurate; often we just do not know the “true” accuracy. Nonetheless, digital soil mappers should be aware of this issue (Grimm and Behrens, 2010) because the soil observations and environmental covariates may not actually overlap (Cressie and Kornak, 2003), both in space and time.

3.4.2 Measurement uncertainty

Soil data managed in WoSIS have been analysed according to a diverse range of analytical procedures in multiple laboratories. A measure for measurement uncertainty is thus desired. Soil-laboratory-specific quality management systems and laboratory proficiency testing (PT) can provide this type of information (GLOSOLAN, 2023; Magnusson and Örne-mark, 2014; Munzert et al., 2007; NATP, 2015; WEPAL, 2019). Calculation of laboratory-specific measurement uncertainty for a single procedure, as well as multiple analytical procedures, will require several measurement rounds (years of observation) and solid statistical analyses (van Leeuwen et al., 2022). Generally, however, this type of information is not provided with the source datasets submitted to the ISRIC data repository. Therefore, pragmatically, we have distilled the required information from the PT literature (Al-Shammari et al., 2018; ICP Forests, 2021a; Kalra and Maynard, 1991; Rayment and Lyons, 2011; Rossel and McBratney, 1998; van Reeuwijk, 1983; WEPAL, 2019), as far as technically feasible. In the case of organic carbon content,

for example, the mean variability was 17 % (with a range of 12 % to 42 %) and for “CEC buffered at pH 7” it was 18 % (range 13 % to 25 %) when multiple laboratories analyse a standard set of reference materials using similar operational procedures (WEPAL, 2019).

The figures for measurement accuracy presented in Appendix A represent first approximations. They are derived from the inter-laboratory comparison of analyses on well-homogenised reference samples for a still relatively small range of soil types. These indicator figures should be refined, for example, using probability distribution functions (Heuvelink et al., 2007; van Leeuwen et al., 2022), once sufficient laboratory and procedure-related accuracy (i.e. systematic and random error) information is provided with the shared soil data (Magnusson and Örnemark, 2014). Alternatively, this type of information may be collated in the context of international laboratory PT networks such as GLOSOLAN and WEPAL and in the framework of the ongoing LUCAS topsoil monitoring round (Bispo et al., 2021; Cornu et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the present first estimates can already be considered when calculating the uncertainty of predictive digital soil maps and of any interpretations derived from them (e.g. studies of soil organic carbon stock change).

Realistically, full harmonisation of analytical data derived from disparate sources, the ultimate ambition in WoSIS, will first become feasible once results of a representative set of multi-procedure, inter-laboratory comparison datasets become (freely) available, as discussed by Baritz et al. (2014), Bispo et al. (2021) and Batjes (2023), and a common set of reference standard operating procedures (SOPs) has been accepted as a global standard.

3.4.3 Year of sampling

For each profile site, the date of sampling has been recorded as far as documented in the source data. This information is important to consider when superimposing the profile data with environmental covariates, such as land cover, for example, in the context of space and time analyses (Giller et al., 2006; Heuvelink et al., 2021). Most (54 %) profiles represented in the snapshot were described/sampled between 1980 and 2020 (Table 3) and less than 4 % before 1960. Alternatively, the date of site description and sampling is not known for almost 27 % of the profiles as the information was not provided in the source materials.

4 Spatial distribution of soil profiles and number of observations

4.1 Spatial distribution

The 2023 snapshot includes standardised data for 228 000 profiles, sampled at 217 000 different sites (Fig. 2). The greatest number of profiles comes from North America

Table 3. Period of sampling/analysis.

Period	<i>N</i> of profiles	Percentage
< 1920	37	0
1920–1940	253	0.1
1940–1960	8632	3.8
1960–1980	35 358	15.5
1980–2000	75 686	33.2
2000–2020	47 768	20.9
Not specified	60 356	26.5

Table 4. Number of soil profiles per continent.

Continent	Number of profiles		
	2023 snapshot	2019 snapshot	2016 snapshot
Africa	32 198	27 688	17 153
Antarctica	35	9	0
Asia	7763	6704	3089
Europe	39 728	35 311	1908
North America	78 996	73 604	63 066
Oceania	43 013	42 918	235
South America	26 457	10 218	8790

(35 %), followed by Oceania (19 %) and Europe (17 %), while there are still few profiles for Asia (3 %) and Antarctica (Table 4). The profiles come from sites in 174 countries. The average density of observations varies greatly both between countries (Table C1) and within each country/area.

Changes in the spatial distribution and density of profiles (per 1000 km²) in the successive WoSIS snapshots (Fig. 3) reflect the degree to which our data acquisition efforts were successful, as further discussed in Sect. 6. Overall, the density of soil observations is still low for central Asia, southeast Asia, central and eastern Europe, Russia, and the northern circumpolar region in the 2023 snapshot.

The number of profiles by biome (R. J. Olson et al., 2001) and broad climatic region (Sayre et al., 2014), as derived from GIS overlays, is listed in Tables C2 and C3.

4.2 Number and depth of observations

In total, the profiles considered in the 2023 snapshot are described by 0.9 million soil layers (or horizons). This corresponds with over 6.1 million records that include both numeric (e.g. silt content, soil pH and cation exchange capacity) and class (e.g. WRB soil classification and horizon designation) properties. There are more observations for the chemical properties than the physical properties (see Table A1). Further, the number of observations generally decreases with depth, largely depending on the objectives of the original soil surveys. The interquartile range (Q1–Q3) for maximum depth of soil sampled in the field is 33–150 cm, with a me-

Figure 2. Distribution of sites represented in the 2023 snapshot of WoSIS (Goode homolosine equal-area projection).

Table 5. Maximum depth of soil sampled per continent.

Continent	Maximum depth sampled (cm)		
	≤ 30	30–60	> 60
Africa	5307	1779	22 458
Antarctica	6	7	17
Asia	635	505	4310
Europe	9411	2848	23 195
North America	6190	6728	60 698
Oceania	9216	3792	27 839
South America	1730	810	8477

dian (Q2) of 100 cm (mean = 107 cm). It should be noted here that most specific purpose surveys only consider the top-soil (e.g. soil fertility surveys), while others systematically sample soil layers up to depths exceeding 20 m (with a maximum of 32 m). When data from such “specific purpose surveys” (defined here as < 30 cm and > 300 cm) are excluded, the figures for maximum depth sampled become Q1 = 90 cm, Q2 = 122 cm and Q3 = 155 cm, with a mean of 126 cm.

Table 5 provides an overview of the maximum depth of soil sampled during the various surveys that underpin WoSIS, by continent. Unfortunately, we are not able to show the “depth to bedrock” as this information is seldom made explicit in the source databases.

5 Distributing the standardised data

The standardised data are distributed through ISRIC’s Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI). The SDI is based on open-source technologies and open web services (WFS, WMS, WCS, CSW) following Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)

standards and aimed specifically at handling soil data. Our metadata are organised following standards of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO-19139, 2019) using GeoNetwork (see <https://data.isric.org>, last access: 26 April 2024). The WoSIS database is hosted in a PostgreSQL database, with the spatial extension PostGIS. The PostgreSQL database itself is connected to MapServer to permit data download from GeoNetwork. These processes are aimed at facilitating global data interoperability and citation in compliance with FAIR principles. The data should be “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable” (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Static snapshots are given a unique DOI (digital object identifier) to permit consistent citation. The 2023 snapshot is distributed in tab-separated values format (see Appendix B for file structure) and as a GeoPackage (<https://doi.org/10.17027/isric-wdcsoils-20231130>; Calisto et al., 2023). An online Readme file, which includes links to two short tutorials, provides additional technical information (https://www.isric.org/sites/default/files/Readme_WoSIS_202312_v2.pdf, last access: 26 April 2024). Alternatively, the evolving dynamic version of the standardised data (i.e. *wosis_latest*) can be accessed/queried through the ISRIC Data Hub (<https://data.isric.org>, last access: 26 April 2024) and the SoilGrids platform (<https://soilgrids.org>, last access: 26 April 2024). Tutorials describing how to access *wosis_latest* from QGIS using WFS and with GraphQL (Calisto, 2023) can be found on the ISRIC website (see <https://www.isric.org/explore/wosis/faq-wosis>, last access: 26 April 2024).

By its nature, the dynamic version will grow when new profile data are shared and processed, additional soil properties are considered in the WoSIS workflow,

Figure 3. Density and spatial distribution of profiles served with the 2016, 2019 and 2023 WoSIS snapshots.

and/or when possible corrections are required. Potential errors can be reported via a “Google group” (<https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/isoric-world-soil-information>, last access: 26 April 2024) so that these may be addressed in the dynamic version.

6 Discussion

We describe new procedures for handling and standardising disparate world soil profile data in WoSIS. The data model was fully harmonised to ISO 25828 and O&M requirements, with minor adjustments, and refactored ETL procedures were implemented. Alternatively, it should be stressed that the ultimate, desired full harmonisation of observations to an agreed reference analytical procedure Y , for example, “pH H_2O ,”

1 : 2.5 soil/water solution” for, say, all “pH 1 : x H₂O” measurements, will first become feasible once the target procedure (Y) for analysing each property has been defined and subsequently accepted as a “global standard” by the international soil community. A next step would be to collate/develop “comparative” datasets for each soil property (i.e. sets with samples analysed according to a given reference procedure (Y_i) and the corresponding national procedures (X_j)) for pedotransfer function development. These relationships, however, will often be soil-type- and region-specific (GlobalSoilMap, 2015) and difficult to develop (i.e. calibrate and validate) when datasets for the comparisons do not yet exist or are simply not freely shared/available (Batjes, 2023; Bispo et al., 2021; Cornu et al., 2023; van Leeuwen et al., 2024). Hence, regional laboratory inter-comparison programmes, such as those undertaken in the framework of, for example, ANSIS (2023), GLOSOLAN (2023), ICP Forests (2021a) and LUCAS (Bispo et al., 2021), which aim to develop consistent, context-specific (e.g. by country or land use/soil type) pedotransfer functions towards an agreed set of SOPs, are important. However, it should be noted that the standard type of SOPs specified by these various programmes need not be comparable. In this context, Suvannang et al. (2018) observed that “comparable and useful soil information (at the global level) will only be attainable once laboratories agree to follow common standards and norms”. Over the years, however, many organisations/countries have implemented analytical procedures and quality assurance systems that are well suited for their specific purposes (e.g. ANSIS, 2023; Cornu et al., 2023; Orgiazzi et al., 2018; Soil Survey Staff, 2022a). Consequently, they may not be inclined to harmonise their data to a (still to be decided) set of global “reference” SOPs. However, agreed-upon procedures for such a full-scale harmonisation will be required when developing a globally federated, and ultimately interoperable, spatial soil data infrastructure (GLOSIS, de Sousa et al., 2021) through which (pre-harmonised) source data are served and updated by the respective data providers and made queryable according to a common standard (de Sousa et al., 2023; OGC, 2019).

It is our intention to gradually fill gaps in the geographic distribution (Fig. 3) and range of soil properties (Appendix A) in the coming years. This work is part of ISRIC’s remit as a regular member of the World Data System (<https://worlddatasystem.org>, last access: 26 April 2024). The degree to which this will be feasible, however, will largely depend on the willingness and ability of data providers to share (some of) their data for consideration in WoSIS. For the northern boreal and Arctic region, for example, ISRIC can draw on new profiles collated by the International Soil Carbon Network (ISCN; see Malhotra et al., 2019). Alternatively, it should be reiterated that several datasets in our repository (e.g. ICP Forests, 2021a) can *only* be standardised and used for SoilGrids™ applications due to existing licence restrictions. Conversely, some countries such as Aotearoa/New Zealand distribute their national soil profile

dataset with a CC-BY-ND 4.0 licence, which implicitly precludes making any derivatives; hence they cannot be considered in WoSIS (see <https://viewer-nsdr.landcareresearch.co.nz/datasets/downloads/1042-2>, last access: 10 June 2024).

Concerning the actual scope for expanding *wosis_latest* in the coming years, we noted that getting positive responses to our requests for sharing soil data is becoming increasingly cumbersome; the overall success rate during the “2019–2023” acquisition effort was around 25 %. However, many of these datasets are being shared with ISRIC with the provision that the profile coordinates themselves may not be shown; hence, the corresponding soil data cannot be “openly” served to our user community through *wosis_latest*. Further, the site and profile coordinates are then regularly shared as “theoretical coordinates” only (e.g. ICP Forests, 2021b; Poeplau et al., 2020), highlighting the need for considering positional uncertainty in digital soil mapping and other applications. Another source of concern is that major soil monitoring programmes, such as LUCAS (e.g. Ballabio et al., 2016; Orgiazzi et al., 2018), only consider the top 20 or 30 cm of the soil. That is, they do not consider the actual soil profile depth as required for more comprehensive soil assessments such as computing changes in global carbon stocks or mapping plant-available water-holding capacity in the root zone (e.g. Batlle-Bayer et al., 2010; Leenaars et al., 2018; von Haden et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022).

7 Data availability

The 2023 snapshot is archived for long-term storage at ISRIC – World Soil Information, the World Data Centre for Soils (WDC-Soils) of the ISC (International Council for Science) World Data System (WDS). It is freely accessible at <https://doi.org/10.17027/isric-wdcsoils-20231130> (Calisto et al., 2023). The zip file (446 Gb) includes a copy of the Readme file and the data in TSV format (see Appendix B) and OGC GeoPackage format.

8 Conclusions

Bringing disparate soil profile data from different sources under a common global standard poses many and diverse challenges. A major improvement has been the harmonisation of the WoSIS data model to ISO 28258 and O&M domain specifications. In conjunction with this, refactored ETL procedures greatly improved the data ingestion and standardisation process, and new ways for visualising, querying and serving the data were developed to better serve our user community.

There are still numerous gaps in terms of geographic distribution as well as the range of soil taxonomic units and/or soil properties represented. We aspire to address such gaps in future updates of *wosis_latest*. However, as the World Data Centre for Soils, we are largely dependent on the ability of soil data owners to share some of their data freely for the

greater benefit of the international community. To facilitate and stimulate this process, we are developing a web-based facility (front-end) to permit data providers to directly upload their soil data to WoSIS in a consistent format based on the refactored ETL procedures. As an incentive, upon their standardisation, we aim to provide each data provider with a tailor-made dashboard for viewing and querying the datasets they shared, possibly with a DOI to facilitate citation.

Various sources of uncertainty are associated with the data. Therefore, we provide three measures for fitness for intended use of the standardised data. This information, although coarse, should be duly considered by prospective users of the snapshot.

Unfortunately, numerous soil datasets worldwide are not freely accessible for various reasons. Standardised procedures, mechanisms, policies and incentives aimed at encouraging soil data sharing by different categories of data owners/providers are needed (e.g. Fantappie et al., 2021; Gobezie and Biswas, 2023; Padarian and McBratney, 2020; Robinson et al., 2019). At a transnational level, these pressing and complex issues are being addressed by the Global Soil Partnership, hosted by UN-FAO, in the context of the evolving federated Global Soil Information System.

Appendix A: Coding conventions

Table A1. Coding conventions for observations (i.e. a combination of property, procedure and unit of measurement), number of profiles and layers provided in the WoSIS 2023 snapshot and inferred accuracy of measurements (codes are listed in alphabetical order).

Code	Property	Procedure ^a	Unit	Profiles	Layers	Accuracy (\pm %) ^b
BDFI33	Bulk density fine earth ^c	Bulk density of a soil sample that has been desorbed to 33 kPa (1/3 bar)	kg dm ⁻³	14 886	78 007	25.0
BDFIAD	Bulk density fine earth	Bulk density of a soil sample that has been air-dried	kg dm ⁻³	4238	14 485	25.0
BDFIFM	Bulk density fine earth	Bulk density of a soil sample at field-soil water content at time of sampling	kg dm ⁻³	5265	14 075	25.0
BDFIOD	Bulk density fine earth	Bulk density of a soil sample that has been dried in an oven at 110 °C	kg dm ⁻³	26 064	131 623	25.0
BDWSAD	Bulk density whole soil ^c	Bulk density of a soil sample that has been air-dried	kg dm ⁻³	0	0	25.0
BDWSOD	Bulk density whole soil	Bulk density of a soil sample that has been dried in an oven at 110 °C	kg dm ⁻³	14 596	75 397	25.0
CECPH7	Cation exchange capacity	CEC estimated by buffering the soil at pH 7 (e.g. NH ₄ Oac)	cmol(c) kg ⁻¹	60 339	320 532	20.0
CECPH8	Cation exchange capacity	CEC estimated by buffering the soil at pH 8 (e.g. BaCl ₂)	cmol(c) kg ⁻¹	6838	25 100	20.0
CFGR	Coarse fragments	Gravimetric content of soil material larger than 2 mm ^c	g per 100 g	39 481	202 414	20.0
CFVO	Coarse fragments	Volumetric content of soil material larger than 2 mm ^c	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	48 891	246 580	30.0
CLAY	Clay ^d	Determination of total gravimetric content of clay size fraction (for class size limits and analytical methods, see “method_options”)	g per 100g	153 319	652 347	15.0
ECEC	Cation exchange capacity	Effective CEC conventionally approximated by summation of exchangeable bases (Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , K ⁺ and Na ⁺) and 1 M KCl exchangeable acidity (Al ³⁺ and H ⁺) in acidic soils	cmol(c) kg ⁻¹	35 123	143 693	25.0
ELCO20	Electrical conductivity	Electrical conductivity assessed on a 1 : 2 soil water extract. Used for saline soils.	dS m ⁻¹	7971	44 350	10.0

Table A1. Continued.

Code	Property	Procedure ^a	Unit	Profiles	Layers	Accuracy (\pm %) ^b
ELCO25	Electrical conductivity	Electrical conductivity assessed on a 1 : 2.5 soil water extract. Used for saline soils.	dS m ⁻¹	4395	17 825	10.0
ELCO50	Electrical conductivity	Electrical conductivity assessed on a 1 : 5 soil water extract. Used for saline soils.	dS m ⁻¹	23 121	90 959	10.0
ELCOSP	Electrical conductivity	Electrical conductivity assessed on water-saturated soil paste. Used for saline soils.	dS m ⁻¹	22 052	85 020	10.0
NITKJD	Total nitrogen (N)	Kjeldahl wet-oxidation digestion procedure	g kg ⁻¹	72 905	240 433	10.0
ORGC	Organic carbon (C)	Amount of organic carbon determined according to method specified under “method_options”	g kg ⁻¹	135 655	526 953	15.0
ORGM	Organic matter	Determination of organic compounds that accompany soil particles through a 2 mm sieve using loss on ignition (LOI) at about 400 °C.	g kg ⁻¹	3871	16 282	15.0
PHAQ	pH	A measure of the acidity or alkalinity in soils, defined as the negative logarithm (base 10) of the activity of hydronium ions (H ⁺) in water ^a .	unitless	140 326	655 336	0.3
PHCA	pH	A measure of the acidity or alkalinity in soils, defined as the negative logarithm (base 10) of the activity of hydronium ions (H ⁺), in the specified CaCl ₂ solution.	unitless	69 437	325 153	0.3
PHKC	pH	A measure of the acidity or alkalinity in soils, defined as the negative logarithm (base 10) of the activity of hydronium ions (H ⁺), in the specified KCl solution.	unitless	38 022	173 464	0.3
PHNF	pH	A measure of the acidity or alkalinity in soils, defined as the negative logarithm (base 10) of the activity of hydronium ions (H ⁺), in the specified NaF solution.	unitless	4965	25 409	0.3
PHETB1	Phosphorus (P)	Phosphorus determined according to the Bray-I method, a combination of HCl and NH ₄ -F to remove easily acid soluble P forms, largely Al and Fe phosphates (mainly applicable for acid soils)	mg kg ⁻¹	10 719	40 379	40.0

Table A1. Continued.

Code	Property	Procedure ^a	Unit	Profiles	Layers	Accuracy (\pm %) ^b
PHETM3	Phosphorus (P)	Determined according to the Mehlich 3 method, a weak acid soil extraction procedure that is considered suitable for removing P and other elements in acid and neutral soil. The extract is composed of 0.2 M glacial acetic acid, 0.25 M ammonium nitrate, 0.015 M ammonium fluoride, 0.013 M nitric acid and 0.001 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA).	mg kg ⁻¹	1444	7230	25.0
PHETOL	Phosphorus (P)	Phosphorus determined according to the Olsen method (0.5 M sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO ₃) solution at a pH of 8.5); used to extract P from calcareous, alkaline and neutral soils.	mg kg ⁻¹	4266	12 291	25.0
PHPRTN	Phosphorus (P)	Phosphorus retention measured according to the New Zealand method (Blakemore et al., 1981).	g per 100 g	5599	26 569	20.0
PHPTOT	Phosphorus (P)	Phosphorus determined with a “harsh” digest procedure to liberate and measure all forms of element.	mg kg ⁻¹	7561	19 310	15.0
PHPWSL	Phosphorus (P)	Phosphorus soluble in soluble in water	mg kg ⁻¹	282	1241	15.0
SAND	Sand	Determination of total gravimetric content of sand size fraction (for class size limits and analytical methods, see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	119 127	542 463	15.0
SILT	Silt ^f	Determination of total gravimetric content of silt size fraction (for class size limits and analytical methods, see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	145 906	620 790	15.0
TCEQ	Calcium carbonate equivalent (TCEQ)	Determination of the gravimetric loss of carbonates as carbon dioxide in the presence of excess hydrochloric acid. The quantity of carbonate (CO ₃) in the soil is expressed as CaCO ₃ and as a weight percentage of the size fraction that is less than 2 mm.	g kg ⁻¹	59 294	247 368	10.0

Table A1. Continued.

Code	Property	Procedure ^a	Unit	Profiles	Layers	Accuracy (\pm %) ^b
TOTC	Total carbon (C)	Total C is quantified by two basic methods: wet or dry combustion (see “method options”). In total C determinations, all forms of C in a soil are converted to CO ₂ followed by a quantification of the evolved CO ₂ . Total C can be used to estimate the organic C content of a soil. The difference between total and inorganic C is an estimate of the organic C.	g kg ⁻¹	33 527	112 787	10.0
WG0006	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 6 kPa (see method options’)	g per 100 g	827	3828	20.0
WG0010	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 10 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	2970	12 517	20.0
WG0033	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 33 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	20 994	94 707	20.0
WG0100	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 100 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	687	3360	20.0
WG0200	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 200 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	4391	27 773	20.0
WG0500	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 500 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	326	1414	20.0
WG1500	Water retention gravimetric	Water retention assessed at tension 1500 kPa (see “method_options”).	g per 100 g	33 782	181 999	20.0
WV0010	Water retention volumetric	Water retention assessed at tension 10 kPa (see “method_options”).	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	1914	6883	20.0
WV0033	Water retention volumetric	Water retention assessed at tension 33 kPa (see “method_options”).	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	7444	22 291	20.0
WV0100	Water retention volumetric	Water retention assessed at tension 100 kPa (see “method_options”).	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	747	2553	20.0

Table A1. Continued.

Code	Property	Procedure ^a	Unit	Profiles	Layers	Accuracy (\pm %) ^b
WV0500	Water retention volumetric	Water retention assessed at tension 500 kPa (see “method_options”).	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	702	1758	20.0
WV1500	Water retention volumetric	Water retention assessed at tension 1500 kPa (see “method_options”).	cm ³ per 100 cm ³	7904	23 331	20.0

^a Method options for each analytical procedure are described in Batjes and van Oostrum (2023) and provided in the *wosis_202312_xxxx.tsv* file; see Appendix C.

^b Inferred accuracy (or uncertainty), rounded to the nearest 5 %, unless otherwise indicated (i.e. units for soil pH), as derived from various sources (Al-Shammary et al., 2018; Kalra and Maynard, 1991; Rayment and Lyons, 2011; Rossel and McBratney, 1998; van Reeuwijk, 1983; WEPAL, 2019). These figures are first approximations that should be fine-tuned once more specific results of laboratory proficiency tests, i.e. national Soil Quality Management systems, become freely available (e.g. from the GLOSOLAN laboratory proficiency programme).

^c Generally, the fine earth fraction is defined as being < 2 mm. Alternatively, an upper limit of 1 mm was used in the former Soviet Union and its satellite states (Katchynsky scheme). The actual size limits are specified under “method_options” (see Appendix C).

^d Provided only when the sum of clay, silt and sand fraction is ≥ 90 and ≤ 100 % (note that users should normalise the totals to 100 % before using them for mapping or modelling purposes; further, more stringent limits (e.g. ≥ 98 and ≤ 102) may be considered).

^e No data are being served for this property because the associated licences are flagged as “restricted” by the data providers.

^f The lower and upper limits for the “silt” size fraction can vary markedly between countries; hence these limits have been specified explicitly in WoSIS under “method_options” (see Appendix B). Development and application of conversion procedures to one common “silt” fraction (e.g. 0.002–0.05 mm) are beyond the remit of the WoSIS project itself. The necessary pedotransfer functions should be developed (and tested) prior to generating particle-size-class-related soil property maps for a given geography. Research in this direction is being undertaken by the SoilGrids team, based on the “best available” comparative datasets for calibration.

Table A2. Coding conventions and brief descriptions for soil classification, horizon designations and number of occurrences in the WoSIS 2023 snapshot.

Code	Description	Count
CSTX	Classification of the soil profile according to specified edition (year) of USDA Soil Taxonomy, at least at soil order level	31 400
CWRB	Classification of the soil profile according to specified edition (year) of the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB), at least at reference soil group level	39 649
CFAO	Classification of the soil profile according to specified edition (year) of the FAO-UNESCO legend, at least at major group level	38 792
HODS ^a	Horizon designations as provided in the source databases	80 849/396 522 ^b

^a Where available, the “cleaned” (original) layer/horizon designation is provided for general information; these codes have not been standardised as they vary widely between different classification systems (Bridges, 1993; Gerasimova et al., 2013). When no horizon designations are provided in the source data bases, we have flagged all layers with an upper depth given as being negative (e.g. –10 to 0 cm, that is using pre-1993 conventions (see Sect. 3.1) in the source databases as likely being a shallow “organic surface” layer above a mineral soil layer.

^b Number of profiles with horizon descriptions as well as the total number of layers with horizon designations.

Appendix B: Structure of the WoSIS 2023 snapshot

This appendix describes the structure of the data files served with the WoSIS 2023 snapshot, namely *wosis_202312_observations.tsv*, *wosis_202312_site.tsv*, *wosis_202312_profiles.tsv*, *wosis_202312_layers.tsv* and *wosis_202312_xxxx.tsv* (where “xxxx” is the name of the observation). The data files are also distributed in OGC GeoPackage format, which stores the files within an SQLite database. Technical details are provided in a Readme file (https://www.isric.org/sites/default/files/Readme_WoSIS_202312_v2.pdf, last access: 26 April 2024).

wosis_202312_observations.tsv. This file lists the four- to six-letter codes for each observation, whether the observation is for a site/profile or layer (horizon), the unit of measurement, and the number of profiles and layers represented in the snapshot. It also provides the inferred accuracy for the laboratory measurements (see Appendix A).

code	Code for the observation
property	Description of soil property
procedure	Description of analytical procedure
unit	Standard unit of measurement
profiles	Number of profiles that have at least one measurement for the observation
layers	Number of layers that have measurements for the observation
accuracy	Inferred accuracy of the laboratory measurements (first approximation; see Sect. 3.4.2)

wosis_202312_site.tsv. This file characterises the site location where profiles were sampled. The following field names are used.

site_id	Primary key
longitude	Longitude in degrees (WGS84)
latitude	Latitude in degrees (WGS84)
positional_uncertainty	Positional uncertainty of the profile’s site location, expressed in four classes (see Table 2)
country_name	Name of country/area where site is located
region	Region in which site is located
continent	Continent in which site is located

wosis_202312_profiles.tsv. Presents the unique profile ID (i.e. primary key), site_id, source of the data, country ISO code and name, positional uncertainty, latitude and longitude (WGS84), and maximum depth of soil described and sampled, as well as information on the soil classification system and edition. Depending on the soil classification system used, the number of fields will vary. For example, for the World Soil Reference Base (WRB) system, the options are

publication year (i.e. version), reference_soil_group_code, reference_soil_group_name, and the name(s) of the prefix (primary) qualifier(s) and suffix (supplementary) qualifier(s). The terms principal qualifier and supplementary qualifier have been used since 2015 (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015, 2022); earlier WRB versions used prefix and suffix for this (e.g. IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Alternatively, for USDA Soil Taxonomy, the version (year), order, suborder, great group and subgroup can be accommodated (Soil Survey Staff, 2014). The following field names are used.

profile_id	Primary key
profile_code	Code for the profile
dataset_code	Identifier for source dataset
site_id	Identifier for site where profile is located
positional_uncertainty	Positional uncertainty of the profile’s site location, expressed in four classes (see Table 2)
country_name	Name of country/area where site is located
longitude	Longitude in degrees (WGS84)
latitude	Latitude in degrees (WGS84)
wrb_reference_soil_group_code	Code for WRB group (in given version of WRB)
wrb_reference_soil_group	Full name for reference soil group
wrb_prefix_qualifiers	Name for prefix (i.e. for WRB1988)
wrb_suffix_qualifiers	Name for suffix (i.e. for WRB1988)
wrb_principal_qualifiers	Name for principal qualifiers (i.e. for WRB 2015 and WRB 2022)
wrb_supplementary_qualifiers	Name for supplementary qualifiers (i.e. for WRB 2015 and WRB 2022)
wrb_publication_year	Version of World Reference Base for Soil Resources
fao_major_group_code	Code for major group (in given version of the legend),
fao_major_group	Name of major group
fao_soil_unit_code	Code for soil unit
fao_soil_unit	Name of soil unit
fao_publication_year	Version of FAO legend (e.g. 1974 or 1988)
usda_order_name	Name of USDA Soil Taxonomy order
usda_suborder	Name of USDA Soil Taxonomy suborder
usda_great_group	Name of USDA Soil Taxonomy greatgroup
usda_subgroup	Name of USDA Soil Taxonomy subgroup
usda_publication_year	Version of USDA Soil Taxonomy

wosis_202312_layers.tsv. This file characterises the layers (or horizons) per profile.

profile_id	Primary key	method_options	Array listing the method options for each analytical procedure as distilled from the source data. (The content of this array varies with the soil observation under consideration as described in the method option table for each analytical procedure. For example, in the case of electrical conductivity (ELCO), the method options include sample pretreatment (e.g. sieved over 2 mm size, solution (e.g. water), ratio (e.g. 1 : 5) and ratio base (e.g. weight / volume)). For details, see Batjes and van Oostrum (2023).)
layer_id	Sequential number for the layer (or horizon)	value_avg	Average, for above (it is recommended to use this value for “routine” modelling)
profile_code	Code for the profile	dataset_id	Abbreviation for source dataset (e.g. WD-ISCN)
site_id	Identifier for site where profile is located	country_name	Name of country/area where site is located
layer_name	Name of pedogenetic horizon (as is)	longitude	Longitude in degrees (WGS84)
upper_depth	Upper depth of layer	latitude	Latitude in degrees (WGS84)
lower_depth	Lower depth of layer	positional_uncertainty	Positional uncertainty of the profile’s site location (see Table 2)
layer_number	Sequential number for the layer (or horizon)	region	Region in which site is located
organic_surface	Flag for the presence of an organic layer above the mineral soil	continent	Continent where the profile’s site is located
dataset_id	Abbreviation for source dataset (e.g. WD-ISCN)	date	Date the profile was described/sampled
licence	Licence for observation as indicated by the data provider (e.g. CC BY)	licence	Licence for given data, as indicated by the data provider (i.e. CC BY or CC BY-NC)
<p><i>wosis_202312_xxxx.tsv</i>. For each observation (e.g. “xxxx” = “BDFIOD”), as defined under “code” in file <i>wosis_202312_observation.tsv</i>, the following are listed.</p>			
profile_id	Primary key		
layer_id	Primary key (number, sequential from top to bottom)		
profile_code	Code for given profile		
layer_name	Name of pedogenetic horizon (as is)		
upper_depth	Upper depth of layer		
lower_depth	Lower depth of layer		
organic_surface	Indicates if there is an organic layer above the mineral surface		
value	Array listing all measurement values for observation “xxxx” for the given layer. (In some cases, more than one observation is reported for a given horizon (layer) in the source, for example four values for TOTC: [1 : 5.4, 2 : 8.2, 3 : 6.3, 4 : 7.7] (see value_avg below).)		

Format. All fields in the above files are tab-delimited, with double quotation marks as text delimiters. File coding is according to the UTF-8 Unicode transformation format.

Using the data. Tutorials for downloading and querying the data, using various platforms, are provided on the WoSIS FAQ web page (<https://www.isric.org/explore/wosis/faq-wosis>, last access: 24 April 2024).

Appendix C: Distribution of sites

Table C1. Number of sites per continent and country/area.

Continent	Country/area ^a	Code	No. of sites	Area (km ²)	Site density (per 1000 km ²)
Africa	Abyei ^b	4	0	9943	0
	Algeria	DZ	10	230 8647	0.004
	Angola	AO	1168	1 246 690	0.937
	Benin	BJ	743	115 247	6.447
	Botswana	BW	994	578 247	1.719
	British Indian Ocean Territory	IO	0	49	0
	Burkina Faso	BF	2023	273 281	7.403
	Burundi	BI	36	26 857	1.34
	Cameroon	CM	1417	465 363	3.045
	Cabo Verde	CV	0	4056	0
	Central African Republic	CF	88	619 591	0.142
	Chad	TD	7	1 265 392	0.006
	Comoros	KM	0	1652	0
	Republic of Congo	CG	70	340 599	0.206
	Côte d'Ivoire	CI	255	321 762	0.793
	Democratic Republic of the Congo	CD	378	2 329 162	0.162
	Djibouti	DJ	0	21 670	0
	Egypt	EG	26	982 161	0.026
	Equatorial Guinea	GQ	0	27 000	0
	Eritrea	ER	0	120 763	0
	Ethiopia	ET	1712	1 129 314	1.516
	Gabon	GA	47	264 022	0.178
	Gambia	GM	0	11 203	0
	Ghana	GH	432	238 842	1.809
	Guinea	GN	128	243 023	0.527
	Guinea-Bissau ^b	GW	15	30 740	0.488
	Hala'ib Triangle ^b	10	0	17 684	0
	Ilemi Triangle ^b	13	0	3179	0
	Kenya	KE	1603	582 342	2.753
	Lesotho	LS	33	30 453	1.084
	Liberia	LR	50	96 103	0.52
	Libya	LY	14	1 620 583	0.009
	Madagascar	MG	130	588 834	0.221
	Malawi	MW	3050	118 715	25.692
	Mali	ML	885	1 251 471	0.707
	Ma'tan al-Sarra ^b	11	0	1993	0
	Mauritania	MR	13	1 038 527	0.013
	Mauritius	MU	0	2014	0
	Mayotte	YT	0	378	0
	Morocco	MA	113	414 030	0.273
	Mozambique	MZ	565	787 305	0.718
	Namibia	NA	1569	823 989	1.904
	Niger	NE	520	1 182 602	0.44
	Nigeria	NG	1402	908 978	1.542
	Réunion	RE	0	2504	0
	Rwanda	RW	1016	25 388	40.018
	Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	SH	0	399	0
São Tomé and Príncipe	ST	0	991	0	
Senegal	SN	312	196 200	1.59	
Seychelles	SC	0	499	0	
Sierra Leone	SL	12	72 281	0.166	

Table C1. Continued.

Continent	Country/area	Code	No. of sites	Area (km ²)	Site density (per 1000 km ²)
	Somalia	SO	245	632 562	0.387
	South Africa	ZA	879	1 220 127	0.72
	South Sudan	SS	82	629 821	0.13
	Sudan	SD	130	1 843 196	0.071
	Eswatini (formerly Swaziland)	SZ	14	17 290	0.81
	Togo	TG	9	56 767	0.159
	Tunisia	TN	60	155 148	0.387
	Uganda	UG	84	241 495	0.348
	United Republic of Tanzania	TZ	1910	939 588	2.033
	Western Sahara ^b	EH	0	268 617	0
	Zambia	ZM	603	751 063	0.803
	Zimbabwe	ZW	413	390 648	1.057
Antarctica	Antarctica	AQ	30	12 537 967	0.002
	Bouvet Island	BV	0	45	0
	French Southern and Antarctic Territories	TF	0	7738	0
	Heard Island and McDonald Islands	HM	0	412	0
	South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands	GS	0	3870	0
Asia	Afghanistan	AF	19	641 827	0.03
	Aksai Chin ^b	1	0	30 666	0
	Armenia	AM	509	29 624	17.182
	Arunachal Pradesh ^b	2	2	67 965	0.029
	Azerbaijan	AZ	28	164 780	0.17
	Bahrain	BH	2	673	2.97
	Bangladesh	BD	207	139 825	1.48
	Bhutan	BT	85	37 674	2.256
	Brunei Darussalam	BN	0	5899	0
	Cambodia	KH	424	181 424	2.337
	China	CN	1644	9 345 214	0.176
	China/India disputed territory ^b	3	0	3526	0
	Christmas Island	CX	0	136	0
	Cocos (Keeling) Islands	CC	0	16	0
	Cyprus	CY	12	9249	1.297
	Democratic People's Republic of Korea	KP	0	122 465	0
	Georgia	GE	18	69 785	0.258
	Hong Kong SAR	HK	2	1081	1.851
	India	IN	199	2 961 118	0.067
	Indonesia	ID	179	1 888 620	0.095
	Iran (Islamic Republic of)	IR	2010	1 677 319	1.198
	Iraq	IQ	14	435 864	0.032
	Israel	IL	17	20 720	0.82
	Jammu and Kashmir ^b	12	4	186 035	0.022
	Japan	JP	197	373 651	0.527
	Jordan	JO	47	89 063	0.528
	Kazakhstan	KZ	52	2 841 103	0.018
	Kuril Islands ^b	5	0	4996	0
	Kuwait	KW	1	17 392	0.057
	Kyrgyzstan	KG	1	199 188	0.005
	Lao People's Democratic Republic	LA	20	230 380	0.087
	Lebanon	LB	10	10 136	0.987
	Macau SAR	MO	0	17	0
	Malaysia	MY	155	329 775	0.47
	Maldives	MV	0	223	0
	Mongolia	MN	9	1 564 529	0.006

Table C1. Continued.

Continent	Country/area	Code	No. of sites	Area (km ²)	Site density (per 1000 km ²)
	Myanmar	MM	0	667 085	0
	Nepal	NP	142	147 437	0.963
	State of Palestine ^b	PS	18	6225	2.892
	Oman	OM	11	308 335	0.036
	Pakistan	PK	45	788 439	0.057
	Paracel Islands ^b	6	0	8	0
	Philippines	PH	78	296 031	0.263
	Qatar	QA	0	11 549	0
	Republic of Korea	KR	23	99 124	0.232
	Saudi Arabia	SA	7	1 925 621	0.004
	Scarborough Reef ^b	7	0	44	0
	Senkaku Islands ^b	8	0	5	0
	Singapore	SG	1	594	1.683
	Spratly Islands ^b	9	0	1	0
	Sri Lanka	LK	73	66 173	1.103
	Syrian Arab Republic	SY	69	188 128	0.367
	Taiwan	TW	35	36 127	0.969
	Tajikistan	TJ	5	142 004	0.035
	Thailand	TH	479	515 417	0.929
	Timor-Leste	TL	0	14 892	0
	Türkiye	TR	69	781 229	0.088
	Turkmenistan	TM	0	555 052	0
	United Arab Emirates	AE	12	71 079	0.169
	Uzbekistan	UZ	9	449 620	0.02
	Vietnam	VN	29	327 575	0.089
	Yemen	YE	284	453 596	0.626
Europe	Albania	AL	97	28 682	3.382
	Andorra	AD	0	475	0
	Austria	AT	128	83 964	1.524
	Belarus	BY	96	207 581	0.462
	Belgium	BE	7013	30 669	228.667
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	32	51 145	0.626
	Bulgaria	BG	134	111 300	1.204
	Croatia	HR	78	56 589	1.378
	Czech Republic	CZ	666	78 845	8.447
	Denmark	DK	72	44 458	1.619
	Estonia	EE	241	45 441	5.304
	Faroe Islands	FO	0	1400	0
	Finland	FI	442	336 892	1.312
	France	FR	3183	548 785	5.8
	Germany	DE	4362	357 227	12.211
	Gibraltar	GI	0	6	0
	Greece	GR	374	132 549	2.822
	Guernsey	GG	0	79	0
	Holy See	VA	0	0	0
	Hungary	HU	1421	93 119	15.26
	Iceland	IS	17	102 566	0.166
	Ireland	IE	124	69 809	1.776
	Isle of Man	IM	0	573	0
	Italy	IT	576	301 651	1.909
	Jersey	JE	0	120	0
	Latvia	LV	102	64 563	1.58
	Liechtenstein	LI	0	151	0
	Lithuania	LT	127	64 943	1.956

Table C1. Continued.

Continent	Country/area	Code	No. of sites	Area (km ²)	Site density (per 1000 km ²)
	Luxembourg	LU	142	2621	54.184
	Malta	MT	0	316	0
	Monaco	MC	0	8	0
	Montenegro	ME	12	13 776	0.871
	Netherlands	NL	958	35 203	27.214
	Norway	NO	507	324 257	1.564
	Poland	PL	796	311 961	2.552
	Portugal	PT	455	91 876	4.952
	Republic of Moldova	MD	35	33 798	1.036
	Romania	RO	113	238 118	0.475
	Russian Federation	RU	1464	16 998 830	0.086
	San Marino	SM	0	60	0
	Serbia	RS	69	88 478	0.78
	Slovakia	SK	161	49 072	3.281
	Slovenia	SI	67	20 320	3.297
	Spain	ES	907	505 752	1.793
	Svalbard and Jan Mayen Islands	SJ	4	63 464	0.063
	Sweden	SE	594	449 212	1.322
	Switzerland	CH	10 928	41 257	264.874
	Republic of North Macedonia	MK	20	25 424	0.787
	Ukraine	UA	462	600 526	0.769
	United Kingdom	GB	1727	244 308	7.069
North America	Anguilla	AI	0	79	0
	Antigua and Barbuda	AG	0	452	0
	Aruba	AW	0	180	0
	Bahamas	BS	0	11 904	0
	Barbados	BB	3	433	6.928
	Belize	BZ	26	21 764	1.195
	Bermuda	BM	0	63	0
	British Virgin Islands	VG	0	154	0
	Canada	CA	8778	9 875 646	0.889
	Cayman Islands	KY	0	269	0
	Clipperton Island	CP	0	9	0
	Costa Rica	CR	560	51 042	10.971
	Cuba	CU	53	110 863	0.478
	Dominica	DM	0	751	0
	Dominican Republic	DO	10	48 099	0.208
	El Salvador	SV	38	20 732	1.833
	Greenland	GL	2	2 165 159	0.001
	Grenada	GD	0	318	0
	Guadeloupe	GP	5	1697	2.947
	Guatemala	GT	28	109 062	0.257
	Haiti	HT	0	27 022	0
	Honduras	HN	38	112 124	0.339
	Jamaica	JM	74	10 965	6.749
	Martinique	MQ	0	1104	0
	Mexico	MX	12 599	1 949 527	6.463
	Montserrat	MS	0	101	0
	Netherlands Antilles	AN	4	790	5.066
	Nicaragua	NI	21	128 376	0.164
	Panama	PA	50	74 850	0.668
	Puerto Rico	PR	280	8937	31.329
	Saint Kitts and Nevis	KN	0	262	0
	Saint Lucia	LC	0	603	0

Table C1. Continued.

Continent	Country/area	Code	No. of sites	Area (km ²)	Site density (per 1000 km ²)
	Saint Pierre and Miquelon	PM	0	233	0
	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	VC	0	427	0
	Trinidad and Tobago	TT	2	5144	0.389
	Turks and Caicos Islands	TC	0	530	0
	United States Minor Outlying Islands	UM	0	348	0
	United States of America	US	56 322	9 315 946	6.046
	United States Virgin Islands	VI	46	352	130.555
Oceania	American Samoa	AS	0	200	0
	Australia	AU	42 767	7 687 634	5.563
	Cook Islands	CK	0	241	0
	Fiji	FJ	6	18 293	0.328
	French Polynesia	PF	0	3967	0
	Guam	GU	15	544	27.579
	Kiribati	KI	0	1020	0
	Marshall Islands	MH	0	268	0
	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FM	75	740	101.343
	Nauru	NR	0	22	0
	New Caledonia	NC	2	18 574	0.108
	Aotearoa / New Zealand	NZ	52	270 415	0.192
	Niue	NU	0	263	0
	Norfolk Island	NF	0	38	0
	Northern Mariana Islands	MP	0	476	0
	Palau	PW	18	451	39.924
	Papua New Guinea	PG	24	462 230	0.052
	Pitcairn Islands	PN	0	49	0
	Samoa	WS	18	2835	6.349
	Solomon Islands	SB	1	28 264	0.035
	Tokelau	TK	0	15	0
	Tonga	TO	0	700	0
	Tuvalu	TV	0	48	0
	Vanuatu	VU	1	12 236	0.082
	Wake Island ^b	WK	0	7	0
	Wallis and Futuna Islands	WF	0	142	0
South America	Argentina	AR	253	2 780 175	0.091
	Bolivia (Plurinational State of)	BO	87	1 084 491	0.08
	Brazil	BR	9262	8 485 946	1.091
	Chile	CL	13 662	753 355	18.135
	Colombia	CO	236	1 137 939	0.207
	Ecuador	EC	94	256 249	0.367
	Falkland Islands (Malvinas) ^b	FK	0	12 084	0
	French Guiana	GF	30	83 295	0.36
	Guyana	GY	43	211 722	0.203
	Paraguay	PY	2	399 349	0.005
	Peru	PE	158	1 290 640	0.122
	Suriname	SR	31	145 100	0.214
	Uruguay	UY	136	177 811	0.765
	Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)	VE	204	912 025	0.224

^a Country names and areas are based on the Global Administrative Unit Layers (GAUL) database; see <https://data.apps.fao.org/map/catalogsrv/eng/catalog.search?id=12691#/metadata/9c35ba10-5649-41c8-bdfc-eb78e9e65654> (last access: 26 April 2024). ^b Disputed territory.

Table C2. Number of sites by World Terrestrial Ecosystems (WTE)*.

Temperature zone	Moisture zone	No. of sites	Percent (%)
Polar	Dry	224	0.1
Polar	Moist	532	0.2
Boreal	Dry	1789	0.8
Boreal	Moist	3398	1.6
Cool temperate	Desert	25	0
Cool temperate	Dry	10 968	5
Cool temperate	Moist	53 245	24.5
Warm temperate	Desert	238	0.1
Warm temperate	Dry	29 209	13.4
Warm temperate	Moist	46 533	21.4
Subtropical	Desert	296	0.1
Subtropical	Dry	25 748	11.8
Subtropical	Moist	17 906	8.2
Tropical	Desert	178	0.1
Tropical	Dry	11 315	5.2
Tropical	Moist	11 095	5.1
No data	–	4674	2.2

* World Terrestrial Ecosystems (WTE) as defined by Sayre (2022). Total may differ from 100 % due to rounding.

Table C3. Number of sites by WWF biome*.

WWF biome	No. of sites	Percent (%)
Boreal forests/taiga	5519	2.5
Deserts and xeric shrublands	13 410	6.2
Flooded grasslands and savannas	792	0.4
Lakes	85	0
Mangroves	765	0.4
Mediterranean forests, woodlands and scrub	24 459	11.3
Montane grasslands and shrublands	2796	1.3
Rock and ice	20	0
Temperate broadleaf and mixed forests	74 068	34.1
Temperate coniferous forests	14 436	6.6
Temperate grasslands, savannas and shrublands	23 890	11
Tropical and subtropical coniferous forests	2363	1.1
Tropical and subtropical dry broadleaf forests	4120	1.9
Tropical and subtropical grasslands, savannas and shrublands	31 376	14.4
Tropical and subtropical moist broadleaf forests	16 478	7.6
Tundra	2072	1
No data	724	0.3

* Biomes defined according to *Terrestrial Ecoregions of the World* (WWF) (D. M. Olson et al., 2001). Total may differ from 100 % due to rounding.

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